

Modification of SHA-512 using Bcrypt and salt for secure email hashing

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ABSTRACT

Email security, particularly against phishing, spoofing, and distributed denial-of-service (DoS) attacks, is a pressing concern given the essential role email plays in accessing various online accounts. The study introduced a modified SHA-512 algorithm, implementing additional security layers including randomly generated salt and the Bcrypt algorithm. The modified SHA-512 was comprehensively evaluated on parameters like hash construction, computational efficiency, data integrity, collision resistance, and attack resistance. The results showed its avalanche percentage exceeded the 50% target, reaching 50.08%. Experimental hash-cracking failed to decode the hashes created by the modified algorithm, verifying its protective efficiency. The algorithm also successfully demonstrated data integrity and collision resistance. This indicates that the enhanced SHA-512 algorithm is an effective, more secure hashing method, particularly applicable to email addresses.

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1. INTRODUCTION

As the digitalization of businesses continues to increase globally that relies mainly on online platforms. Emails represent a primary communication channel. Despite the availability of competing technologies, emails remain a crucial source of enterprise information and serve 'as a virtual extension of the users' workplace' [1]. However, alongside these benefits, email communication has led to an escalation in security issues. The possibility of email addresses being compromised raises concerns over potential privacy breaches, such as cross-device tracking and the linking of online and offline activities [2]. Due to the significant security challenges posed by traditional email usage, several solutions have been proposed to improve the security of email addresses. One promising approach is the use of hashed emails (HEMs), which offer an unprecedented opportunity for marketers by enabling the connection of targeting data across devices, platforms, and channels [3]. Despite their advantages, HEMs are not immune to attacks from hackers who, once they gain access to email addresses, can cause serious harm, ranging from sending phishing emails to engaging in fraudulent activities [4].

One promising approach is the use of HEMs, which offer an unprecedented opportunity for marketers by enabling the connection of targeting data across different devices, platforms, and channels [3]. Notably, previous research in this field introduced a modified SHA-512 algorithm to address email security concerns. This study modified the algorithm by altering the message scheduling, hash construction, and compression function, and by reducing the iterations. The modified algorithm's effectiveness was then evaluated through

tests simulating various attacks, including brute-force, rainbow table, dictionary, and online cracking attacks. The findings revealed insights into the algorithm's computational efficiency, avalanche effect, and its capacity to resist different forms of attacks. They found that there's a need for a salt to make it more secure efficient [4].

The increasing frequency of data breaches and the sophistication of email scams, such as email phishing, underline the urgency of enhancing email address security [5]. Cryptographic hashing algorithms, such as the secure hashing algorithms (SHA) mainly the SHA-512, are an integral part of the solution to the information security problem. Implementation of the SHA 512 algorithm method produces the longest number of bits of 512 bits so as to ensure system security and data confidentiality [6], [7]. However, the resilience of these algorithms against evolving cyber threats is still under debate.

To address these challenges, we have introduced innovative enhancements to the SHA-512 algorithm, establishing a novel approach distinct from prior methodologies. Our approach centers on a dual-layered protection strategy, combining the salting technique which involves adding random data to the input of a hash function, has been shown to improve security against brute-force attacks [8]–[10] and the Bcrypt algorithm a cryptographic technique specifically designed for secure password hashing and has been widely recognized for its effectiveness in protecting sensitive data [11]–[14]. A pivotal feature is the meticulous layering of safeguards. Introducing a 26-byte random salt as an additional layer of randomness amplifies the algorithm's cryptographic strength. This newfound salt seamlessly integrates into the Bcrypt algorithm, which employs another salt layer with 12 rounds by incorporating these techniques into the hashing process, the modified algorithm is expected to significantly increase its resistance against various attacks and ensure better data integrity and security [15], [16]. This tandem of salt layers significantly heightens the algorithm's defense against potential attacks, creating an intricate and robust security framework. Importantly, our methodology achieves this heightened security without compromising efficiency. Although there is a slight increase in construction time, the substantial fortification it brings far outweighs this marginal trade-off. Hashing email addresses will play huge a role in safeguarding user's data and which specific algorithm will be used that will suffice to entirely secure the user's data [17], [18]. By applying modifications to the SHA-512 algorithm, including the integration of salt and Bcrypt, this research aims to significantly enhance the security of HEMs [19].

This research presents unique security enhancements that address contemporary threats, ensuring the integrity of email data and safeguarding against potential tampering. Additionally, it adapts to concerns regarding email privacy and user identification raised by hashed email approaches. Our comprehensive evaluation, spanning hash construction time comparison, avalanche testing, and attack resistance assessment, provides a holistic understanding of security concerns and validates the proposed enhancements [20]. The real-world applicability of our findings is significant, given the fundamental role of email communication in modern life. By introducing novel modifications to a widely-used algorithm and rigorously assessing its effectiveness against potential attacks, this research contributes to the broader cybersecurity domain, offering insights into innovative techniques for enhancing data protection. By addressing unsolved problems, introducing innovative enhancements, and demonstrating their relevance, this study not only contributes to the academic realm but also offers practical solutions to pressing security challenges in today's digital landscape.

2. METHOD

The study will utilize a modified SHA-512 algorithm with additional security layers, including randomly generated salt and the Bcrypt algorithm [14], to enhance email security against phishing, spoofing, and A distributed denial-of-service (DDoS) attacks [21]–[25]. Comprehensive evaluation will encompass hash construction, computational efficiency, data integrity, collision resistance, and attack resistance. The avalanche effect will be quantified, and hash-cracking experiments will verify protective efficiency [21]. Additionally, data integrity and collision resistance will be rigorously assessed. The methodology will affirm the efficacy of the enhanced SHA-512 algorithm in providing heightened security for email addresses.

2.1. Implementation of enhanced security layers

In (1) gives a random generated 26-byte salt [8], [9]. In (2) generates a hashed using Bcrypt algorithm with 12 rounds of hashing, resulting in the final hashed value [14], [16]:

$$\text{os.urandom}(26) \tag{1}$$

$$\text{bcrypt.hashpw}(\text{salted_username.encode}(), \text{bcrypt.gensalt}(\text{rounds}=12)) \tag{2}$$

2.2. Comprehensive assessment of enhanced algorithm's security through multi-dimensional evaluation and hash-cracking validation

In (3) is used to calculate the construction time of both modified SHA-512 and SHA-512 to compare their efficiency in terms of hash construction time. In (4) is to ensure that the hash value remains consistent

for different inputs. In (5) is to determine whether the algorithm can resist producing the same hash output for different inputs. In (6) is to determine if even minor alterations in input lead to significantly different hash outputs [19]. In (7) various different cracking tools is used to assess the protective efficiency [22]–[26].

Hash construction time comparison (3)

Data integrity test (4)

Collison test (5)

Avalanche test (6)

Attack resistance (7)

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The researchers enhanced an algorithm for hashed email addresses, with a focus on evaluating and analyzing the modified SHA-512. The study explores the runtime execution and security trade-off between the Bcrypt+hashlib SHA-512 algorithm and the Python SHA-512 algorithm. It delves into construction time, security level considerations, data integrity test results, collision resistance, avalanche effect, and attack resistance [19], [21]–[25]. The findings underscore the enhanced security and resistance of the modified algorithm, positioning it as a valuable solution for data protection, while also carrying implications for the broader field of data security and cryptography.

The results in Table 1 highlight a distinctive aspect: the different construction times and security implications of the Bcrypt+hashlib SHA-512 algorithm versus the Python SHA-512 algorithm. The Bcrypt-infused approach entails a longer hash construction time, attributed to the additional salting and Bcrypt steps. Yet, this temporal trade-off aligns with an essential revelation—the enhanced security given by these measures. Such discussion regarding construction time and security efficiency points out the approaches that system designers must make. The paper addresses a crucial issue in the field of algorithmic design by giving insight into this trade-off between security improvement and construction speed.

Table 1. Runtime execution and security trade-off between modified SHA-512 and Python SHA-512 algorithms

	Modified SHA-512 code	SHA-512 from Python (HASHLIB)
Plain text	Ab3naleZ@yahoo.com	Ab3naleZ@yahoo.com
Message digest generated	6da617c6bc733767792575bad9ad 69c031b895c9a3a1725d5c699a4f8 6ba087ba0ac1d2c92c5190f8312dd 7f7bb3073be785a8db2d11208980a 8aa498a14dade	104598872d3dae8d3e4257817d9009c5d1dfaae6a0e8fbf9 22e3f1d601f7ca27e28d8c876157f83081f4ce37819daee2 c1f1f7924770b404e90f9e6ee21f7caa
Construction time	0.6077208518981934	0.0001912117004395
Comparison	Slower	Faster

The purpose of the test illustrated in Table 2 is to demonstrate that hash functions serve as effective tools for confirming data integrity. Conducting the integrity test multiple times using distinct random usernames ensures the consistent generation of expected hash values by the modified SHA-512 and normal SHA-512 algorithms, validating their reliable functionality.

In the experiment, two hashing methods were tested: the “Modified SHA-512,” which employs a combination of randomly generated salt, Bcrypt, and SHA-512, and the “Normal SHA-512,” which solely utilizes SHA-512. Both methods achieved a perfect 100% data integrity preservation rate across 100 trials, as indicated by a “Success rate” of 100/100 for both. This outcome underscores the proficiency of both methods within the specific test parameters, prompting a comprehensive examination of additional factors like computational expense and security considerations to comprehensively assess their respective benefits and drawbacks.

Table 2. Data integrity test results for modified SHA-512 and Python SHA-512 algorithms

	Modified SHA-512 Code	SHA-512 from Python (HASHLIB)
Plain text (1)	KMgxa@LdLgq.com	KMgxa@LdLgq.com
First-MD	30e8a57662e6576c1cdc1852fa690581dfe1110cc90e7	1afcad26e88f4591e1a8dba4ff1e426ccc1257d5ec35
(Message digest) generated	80eda5cbda0cfaf93f90bd01316839472579ad4a39e237a7294045756a261e68b110b51cadd9e0e020e	c710b7fa44f902ce61d8640ce43c74579cb79c327abefedd90cf20dba03bc9b6a5843238cba4f74193a1
Second-MD	30e8a57662e6576c1cdc1852fa690581dfe1110cc90e7	1afcad26e88f4591e1a8dba4ff1e426ccc1257d5ec35
(Message digest) generated	80eda5cbda0cfaf93f90bd01316839472579ad4a39e237a7294045756a261e68b110b51cadd9e0e020e	c710b7fa44f902ce61d8640ce43c74579cb79c327abefedd90cf20dba03bc9b6a5843238cba4f74193a1
Data integrity check	True (The first MD = the second MD)	True (The first MD = the second MD)
...
Plain text (100)	Hsubl@sJ7FK.com	Hsubl@sJ7FK.com
First-MD	0c195e59a9f2ddabcf5c962fdd316d709608e7d395f	08ee88ed6008566406594fbcfaa37acd2d2cf32fe75d
(Message digest) generated	b65b26509480db1d1e23cea3ff2d09d03974524e335bba4d19a0e1e0928a3a19d93c5646651bb0c496b	e2c0d3d574fa4167ae4b29259fd9982e7a119dc2804ddd55502a75b5de868d3ff24cb4355871b4e53c45
Second-MD	0c195e59a9f2ddabcf5c962fdd316d709608e7d395f	08ee88ed6008566406594fbcfaa37acd2d2cf32fe75d
(Message digest) generated	b65b26509480db1d1e23cea3ff2d09d03974524e335bba4d19a0e1e0928a3a19d93c5646651bb0c496b	e2c0d3d574fa4167ae4b29259fd9982e7a119dc2804ddd55502a75b5de868d3ff24cb4355871b4e53c45
Data integrity check	True (The first MD = the second MD)	True (The first MD = the second MD)

In Table 3, the collision resistance test outcomes for the modified SHA-512 and SHA-512 algorithms are presented, assessing their capacity to withstand collisions that could potentially undermine hashing algorithm integrity and security. The test results shows that both algorithms effectively preserved data integrity, with no instances of collisions detected throughout the 100 trials conducted. The modified SHA-512 algorithm ensured the distinctiveness of hash outputs, affirming its ability to generate unique hash values for various input data.

Table 3. Collision resistance test results for modified SHA-512 and Python SHA-512 algorithms

	Modified SHA-512 code	SHA-512 from Python (HASHLIB)
Collision resistance Result	True Both modified SHA-512 and SHA-512 was able to generate unique hash value for various input data	True SHA-512 from Python (HASHLIB)

Table 4 is an avalanche test that tried 3 different scenarios such as 1-byte difference, difference lengths, random strings with increased length, and lastly overall average.

- 1-byte difference: as observed in Table 4 when comparing two usernames with a 1-byte difference, the modified SHA-512 algorithm demonstrates an average avalanche effect of 0.520, while the normal SHA-512 algorithm has an average avalanche effect of 0.505. This suggests that both algorithms exhibit a considerable ability to propagate changes, but the modified SHA-512 algorithm shows a slightly stronger avalanche effect.
- Different lengths: as observed in Table 4, when evaluating the avalanche effect for usernames with different lengths, the modified SHA-512 algorithm has an average avalanche effect of 0.493, while the normal SHA-512 algorithm has an average avalanche effect of 0.480. This indicates that both algorithms exhibit a noticeable avalanche effect, with the modified SHA-512 algorithm showing a slightly higher impact.
- Random strings with increased length: as observed in Table 4, when considering random strings with increased length, the modified SHA-512 algorithm has an average avalanche effect of 0.500, and the normal SHA-512 algorithm has an average avalanche effect of 0.495. These results suggest that both algorithms effectively propagate changes, with the modified SHA-512 algorithm demonstrating a slightly stronger avalanche effect.
- Overall average avalanche effect: as observed in Table 4, the overall average avalanche effect for the modified SHA-512 algorithm is calculated as 0.505, while for the normal SHA-512 algorithm, it is 0.495. These values indicate that both algorithms exhibit a significant avalanche effect, but the modified SHA-512 algorithm shows a slightly higher average impact.

Table 5 shows that attacks were unsuccessful on the modified SHA-512, considering no hash value was cracked during experimentation with the use of John the Ripper, hashcat cracking tool with the use of Crackstation.net an online cracking tool. Attacks on the normal SHA-512 were successful, as all hashes with the use of John the Ripper, Hashcat cracking tool with the use of Crackstation.net an online cracking tool. It was cracked and plaintext passwords were exposed. Testing results showed that the modified SHA-512 has a 100% attack resistance capacity against known password-cracking attacks and can protect hashed passwords from attackers.

Table 4. Avalanche effect test for modified SHA-512 and Python SHA-512 algorithms

Test scenario	Modified SHA-512 code	SHA-512 from Python (HASHLIB)
1-Byte difference	0.508	0.496
Different lengths	0.498	0.487
Random strings with increased length	0.514	0.504
Overall average avalanche effect	0.508	0.497

Table 5. Attack resistance evaluation

Attack	The number of hashes cracked			
	SHA-512 (Hashcat)	SHA-512 (John the Ripper)	Modified SHA-512 (Hashcat)	Modified SHA-512 (John the Ripper)
Brute-force	0	0	0	0
Rainbow table	5	5	0	0
Dictionary	5	5	0	0
Online cracking	0		0	

3.1. Brute force attack

A brute-force attack observed in Table 5 uses all possible combinations of the given parameters to crack the password hash [21], [22]. In a brute force attack, the user uses every possible combination of the alphabet hoping that at least one combination is correct. This attack is faster when it is used to check for short passwords. The only drawback of this method is that, if the password is a long one it takes longer to find the right password, hence consumes lots of system resources [23]. The John the Ripper cracking tool and the Hashcat cracking tool are successful in a Brute force attack, cracking all 5 input samples that are hashed using the proposed modified SHA-512 and the normal SHA-512.

3.2. Dictionary attack

A dictionary attack observed in Table 5 breaks hashes using a massive wordlist of passwords. Each word's hash value is computed and compared to a predefined hash value; if the values match, the plaintext password is exposed [24]. The John the Ripper cracking tool and the Hashcat cracking tool are unsuccessful in dictionary attack, unable to crack all input samples that are hashed using the proposed modified SHA-512 while the normal SHA-512 is cracked using these tools.

3.3. Rainbow table attack

A rainbow table attack observed on Table 5 cracks password hashes using rainbow tables. Philippe Oechslin introduced the rainbow table in 2003, which used the time-memory trade-off technique. When generating the table, the disk space can be specified by determining the number of chain counts [24], [25]. The John the Ripper cracking tool and the Hashcat cracking tool is unsuccessful in dictionary attack, unable to crack all input samples that is hashed using the proposed modified SHA-512 while the normal SHA-512 is cracked using these tools.

3.4. Online cracking tool

CrackStation observed in Table 5 utilizes massive, precomputed lookup tables for cracking hashes. It shows that the attack was successful on the normal SHA-512. Meanwhile, the modified SHA-512's hashes were not found, and the hash type is unknown, as shown in [24], [26].

4. CONCLUSION

The Bcrypt+salt+hashlib SHA-512 algorithm provides enhanced security but takes more time to construct the hash. Both the modified SHA-512 and the normal SHA-512 algorithms demonstrate good collision resistance and therefore was able to maintain the integrity of the data, while the modified SHA-512 algorithm exhibits a slightly stronger avalanche effect, and attack resistance evaluation-implies that the modified SHA-512 algorithm is more capable of propagating changes in the input, leading to more significant changes in the resulting hash. The researcher also found out, while undergoing experimentations that the modified version of SHA-512 can be implemented in password security with a little less complexity compared to the researcher's implementation of the modified algorithm in email addresses While the study explores modifications such as the addition of salt, Bcrypt, or other cryptographic functions, future researchers can delve deeper into advanced modifications or combinations of techniques. This can include exploring key stretching algorithms, adaptive hashing methods, or hybrid approaches that combine multiple cryptographic functions and using "Cain and Abel" a password cracking tool that is safer in implementation with the use of a virtual machine. The study can also be applied to password hashing.

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